

Translation of Cultural Terms in Literary Work “*Ini Banyuwangi Sri Tanjung Hidup Kembali*”

Sang Ayu Isnu Maharani¹, I G A Istri Aryani²

^{1,2} Faculty of Humanities, Udayana University, Jalan Pulau Nias 13 Denpasar, Bali-Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This research is descriptive qualitative research entitled "Translation of Cultural Terms in Literary Work "*Ini Banyuwangi Sri Tanjung Hidup Kembali*-This is Banyuwangi Sri Tanjung Comes to Life". This writing is written based on the phenomenon of difficulties in translating cultural terms in many literary works. To be able to provide good translation results, a translator must understand the culture of the source language (SL) and also the target language (TL).

The aim of this research is to identify cultural terms of the literary work. This research also tries to examine the translation strategies applied to translate cultural terms in this literary works.

The research method applied for this research is a documentation method with note taking technique. This research applies Newmark's theory to identify cultural terms and also the Translation Strategy to examine the translation strategies used to translate cultural terms.

The research results showed that there were thirty-two cultural terms translated from the source language (Indonesian) into the target language (English) and contained three categories of cultural terms proposed by Newmark. The categorization of cultural terms found are ecological culture, material culture, and social organization. The translation strategies applied in translating cultural terms of this literary work are found seven of eight strategies mentioned by Newmark. The dominant strategy applied is adaptation strategy, followed by word for word and literal translation strategy. The least strategy applied is idiomatic translation.

KEYWORDS: Banyuwangi, cultural terms, literary work, strategy, translation.

INTRODUCTION

Translation has played significant role in human and social interactions. It contributes to a better comprehension because translation involves interpretation of meaning and later proceeded by rediscovery of meaning. Meaning becomes the core elements that linguistic units considered in the process of translation. This is highlighted by Newmark in his statement. Newmark (1981:27) defines translation as the process of transferring the meaning of a series or linguistic unit, of the whole or part of a text from one language to another. Other linguists also contribute to the comprehension of translation by proposing following definitions. Hatim & Mason (2004:26) state that translation is an activity that can clearly prove the role of language in social life. Meanwhile, Larson (1984:3) states that translation is the transfer of meaning from the source language to the target language. Larson also defines translation more broadly, it stated that translating is an activity that consists of three things: a) researching the lexicon, communication situation, grammatical structure and cultural context in the source language; b) analysing the source language text to find its meaning; and c) re-express the same meaning using lexicon and grammatical structures appropriate to the target language. Catford (1965: 20) believes that translation is the transfer of text from the source language to the equivalent text in the target language.

Translating literary works is significant, interesting yet also challenging. This matter is important to be discussed due to the reason that we can examine how language in particular cultural words, terms or expression are applied in literary works. A translator will find no exact equivalent between one and another language because the culture of both languages, the source language (ST) and the target language (TL) are different; there is no equivalent between two different cultures. (Larson, 1998: 61). This enables translator to choose the option of focusing on source language or target language, or the source or target culture. The important part that needs to be remembered by a translator is that in translating texts which contain major cultural words, terms or expression, a translator is required to be bilingual or multilingual and also to be bicultural or multicultural (Vermeer, 1986:39).

We aware that language and culture are inseparable and interrelated. Language is the key to unlock culture, because to be able to

understand a culture, we need to understand the language used. Culture is a way of life that includes beliefs, symbols, behavior, knowledge, attitude and values which characterized people or organization. To have the ability understanding both is certainly not easy, but once a translator is successful translating the texts, it can help people to give better understanding in the whole narration, ideology and other conceptual facts.

There are previous researches that concerns with translation. Fajar Nur Indriyany in her article entitled "Translation Strategy for Words with a Cultural Concept in Novel Translation of The Great Gatsby" wrote and analyzed the strategy for translating words with a cultural concept in the novel The Great Gatsby. The theories used are Newmark's theory regarding cultural categories and Baker's regarding translation strategies. The data source was obtained from the novel The Great Gatsby by F. Scott Fitzgerald and its translation by Ulya Nataresmi. This paper uses a comparative descriptive approach. The results of the analysis show that there are fifty-five vocabularies with cultural concepts in the categories of ecology, material, social and organizational. The translator used two strategies in translating the novel The Great Gatsby into Indonesian, they are; cultural word replacement strategies in the TL and loan word strategies.

Eky Kusuma Hapsari et al in their research entitled "Strategy for Translating the Terms Social Culture and Social Organization of the Novel Bocchan by Natsume Soseki into Indonesian" examined cultural terms in Japanese. It is stated that not all terms in Japanese can be translated into Indonesian. Therefore, a translation strategy is needed to find cultural equivalents. The results of the research show that there are 72 cultural words or terms, including culture social and organizational culture. The strategies used include applying borrowed language accompanied by explanations, paraphrasing, cultural substitution, paraphrasing of unrelated words, translation using common words, and word deletion.

Sudana, et al (2014) analyzed the translation of cultural terms in the novel Negeri 5 Menara. This research aims to determine the categories of cultural terms contained in novels translated into English, as well as determine the translation procedures applied in translating these cultural terms. Descriptive qualitative methods and Newmark's (1988) translation theory were applied in this research to analyze data on cultural terms. The results show that there are 75 cultural terms, which are broken down into several categories, there are 2 (2.66%) ecological terms, 50 (66.66%) material culture terms, 5 (6.66%) socio-cultural terms, 16 (21, 3%) terms of organization, tradition, activity and concept, and 2 (6.66%) terms of gesture or habit. Of the 12 translation procedures described by Newmark, 7 procedures are applied by translators in translating cultural terms, including; literal translation (16%), descriptive equivalence (12%), transference (29%), generic word (29%), calque (1.33%) additional explanation (4%), couplet with generic word and descriptive equivalence (1.33%). There are 5 cultural terms that are not translated (6.66%) of the total cultural terms.

Anjarsari (2014) discusses translation strategies for cultural terms in the comic "Tintin's Adventure Story: Cigar Sang Faraoh". This research aims to find out the translation strategies for cultural terms used by translators from English into Indonesian. This research applies a descriptive qualitative approach, the data used for this research were taken from cultural terms in comics in the source language and their translations. This research applies theory translation from Newmark (1988) in examining the strategies applied in the process of translating cultural terms in comics. The research results show that there are eight translation strategies, namely; transference, naturalization, reduction, literalization, cultural equivalent, particularization, generalization. The most widely used strategy is the cultural equivalence strategy adapted to the target language (Indonesian), where there are various expressions, words, phrases, sentences and even songs that are translated as naturally as possible.

Utami (2019) studied translation techniques for Chinese cultural terms into Indonesian terms by D3 Chinese language students at Jenderal Soedirmam University. This research aims to identify translation techniques for Chinese cultural terms by D3 Mandarin students, find out the implications of translation techniques for omitting and adding translation meanings and the impact of omitting and adding translation meanings on translation results. This type of research is qualitative research using descriptive methods based on translation theory from Molina and Albir (2002). The research results show that two variants are used in translating cultural terms, 12 single variant translation techniques and 9 double variant translation techniques.

Techniques that show the loss of translation meaning are generalization, borrowing, adaptation, reduction, particulation, kalke and borrowing, generalization techniques.

Those previous researches on translation give valuable insight to the writing of this research. Cultural issues become major prime in the all above discussion. American literature, Japanese novel, comic and also oral data are those applied as source data in the previous researches mentioned above. However, this research tries to explore the local wisdom through local folktales which

contribute to the richness of national literature. The reputation of the writer as one of the well-known anthropologists and also the collaboration among various researchers and scientists mapping the historical collective memory to justify the folklore provide strong reason why this literary work needs to be researched.

Based on the brief introduction and the previous researches, this research tries to answer the following formulated questions, such as: (1) the type of cultural terms translation of literary work of *Ini Banyuwangi Sri Tanjung Hidup Kembali*, (2) the strategy applied for cultural terms translation of literary work of *Ini Banyuwangi Sri Tanjung Hidup Kembali*. The results of this research are expected to have theoretical and practical benefits. The theoretical benefit aims to broaden the reader's insight, concerning Translation. This research is also expected to be able to give insight practically to the translator or those who are interested learning translation study

METHOD

This research is documentary research by applying note taking technique. It is descriptive qualitative research, research which describe and observe the characteristics of a phenomenon being studied. According to Cresswell (1994: 195) a qualitative study focuses on participants' perception and experiences which are presented with words". The data collected by identifying the cultural terms found in the source text (ST) of the literary work and later classified the collected data according the cultural terms classification proposed by Newmark. The cultural terms translation of the target text (TT) later analyzed to find out the strategies applied in the writing.

The source data of this research is a literary book entitled "*Ini Banyuwangi Sri Tanjung Hidup Kembali*". The source text (ST) of the data in Indonesian and the target text (TT) is in English version. The book is written by Aekanu Hariyanto, a well-known anthropologist from Banyuwangi who has strong concern with culture and literature. He collaborates with foreign academics and researchers to produce this translated book.

The collected data is analyzed by applying Newmark theory of cultural term categorization and also its translation strategy. According to Newmark (1988, 94-103), cultural words are divided into 5 categories, they are (a) ecology (plants, animals, mountains, geographical names), (b) material culture (food, clothes, housing, transport), (c) social culture (work and leisure), (d) organization, customs, ideas (political, social, legal), (e) gestures and habits (nonlinguistic features).

This research also applied translation procedure proposed by Newmark, as one of the strategies in translation. Translation procedures are required to translate various cultural expressions. The difference between translation procedures and translation methods have been highlighted by Newmark (1988:81). He mentioned that while translation methods relate to whole texts, translation procedures are used for sentences and the smaller units of language. Newmark (1998: 81-93) proposed eight strategies of translation, they are (1) word for word, (2) literal, (3) faithful, (4) semantic, (5) adaptation, (6) free, (7) idiomatic, (8) communicative.

Word for word translation is generally considered as the rendering of text from an original language to the target language by following the exact words of the original text while sense for sense translation emphasizes the idea of preserving the meaning of the write up without obeying the exact grammar. A literal translation is a translation that follows closely the form of the source language. Faithful translation reproduces the exact contextual meaning of the original within the limits of the grammatical structures or forms of the target language. It transfers cultural terms and preserves the degree of grammatical and lexical faithfully to the intentions of the source language writer. (Newmark, 1988). Semantic translation attempts to render as closely as the semantic and syntactic structure of the target language, allow the exact contextual meaning of the original. Semantic translation is accurate but may not communicate properly. Adaptation translation can be considered as the freest form of translation; it can be found mainly in plays (drama and poetry) and usually the SL culture is being translated into the Target Language culture. Free translation tries to reproduces the meaning without considering the form of the Source Language. Often, this type represents paraphrase much longer than the original. Idiomatic translation reproduces the message of the original but tends to distort nuance of meaning by preferring colloquialisms and idioms. Communicative translation attempts to render the exact contextual meaning of the original in such a way that both content and language are readily acceptable and comprehensible to the readership.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research analyzed the cultural terms of a literary work and also the translation strategy applied within the literary work.

A. Cultural Terms of Literary Work “*Ini Banyuwangi Sri Tanjung Hidup Kembali*”

This subchapter presents cultural words, terms or expression found in the literary work entitled “*Ini Banyuwangi Sri Tanjung Hidup Kembali*”. Each categorization is included in the list of tables as the representative data. This research found that there are total thirty two data of cultural words, terms or expression. It includes ecological culture, material culture and social organization. The followings are the representation of data found in the literary work

1. Ecological Culture

Ecological culture by Newmark includes flora, fauna and geographical names.

Negeri Sindurejo rakyatnya Makmur (ST)

The people of Sindurejo were prosperous (TT)

The above data shows the cultural term of ecological culture that concern about geographical name. The phrase ‘*negeri Sindurejo*’ is translated into ‘**the people of Sindurejo**’ which syntactically is not equivalent but the meaning represented in the TT. The word ‘negeri’ is equal to ‘country’ or ‘land’ in English. However, the translation in the TT is written ‘the people’ because it also represents the land.

Other instances can also be found in the following sentences

Merasa ada tamu yang akan menemuinya, Begawan Tamba Petra yang sakit itu segera mengubah wujudnya menjadi **macan hitam**..... (ST)

Later, as the healer Begawan Tamba Petra began to sense that a visitor was approaching, he changed his form into **black tiger** (TT)

The above data shows cultural term of ecological culture of fauna. The phrase ‘*macan hitam*’ is translated into ‘**black tiger**’.

B. Material Culture

Material culture includes culinary, beverage, housing, cloth, city and transportation.

The following examples are elucidated as follows:

Atas ijin Sang Begawan, diboyonglah Sri Tanjung oleh Sidapaksa ke **Istana Kepatihan** (ST) With the permission of Begawan, Sidapaksa brought Sri Tanjung to **Kepatihan Palace** (TT)

The above data shows the material culture of housing; a traditional house. We can find the phrase ‘Istana Kepatihan’ is translated into ‘Kepatihan Palace’.

Sri Tanjung segera menyerahkan **selendang warisan dari ayahnya** yang berasal dari Kayangan kepada suaminya (ST)

Sri Tanjung gave Sidapaksa **a shawl she had inherited from her father** (TT)

Another example of material culture of clothing; part of traditional cloth. It can be found in the bold phrase above. ‘*Selendang warisan dari ayahnya*’, the translation in the TT is ‘a shawl she had inherited from her father’.

C. Organization, Customs, Ideas

Sebagai seorang **ksatria**, ia berusaha bersabar untuk memutuskan apa yang harus dilakukannya (ST)

As a knight, he tried to remain patient in deciding what to do (TT)

Sidapaksa mengerahkan **ajian** yang mengeluarkan api.... (ST) Sidapaksa concentrated **all of his energy** into a pulse of fire..... (TT)

Cultural terms that found in the above sentences are ‘*ksatria*’ which is translated into ‘**as a knight**’ and also the lexical ‘*ajian*’ which is translated into ‘**all of his energy**’.

B. Translation Strategies of Cultural Terms in Literary Work *Ini Banyuwangi-Sri Tanjung Hidup Kembali*

This part analyzed the translation strategies of cultural terms applied in the literary work. The cultural terms found of the above data were categorized into ecological culture, material culture and organization, customs and ideas. The cultural terms of ecological culture are:

a. *Negeri Sindurejo* (ST) – the people of Sindurejo

This cultural term applied adaptation strategy because there is a change of the cultural element from the Source Text (ST) into the TT which has similarity or familiar to the readership. The word '*negeri*' which should be translated into 'land' in the TT, is represented in the lexical of 'the people'.

b. *Macan hitam* (ST)-black tiger

This term is translated by applying the literal strategy. This strategy emphasized on the literal meaning of the ST and usually the meaning of the word of the ST can be found in the dictionary

The cultural terms of material culture are represented with following sentences, they are:

c. *Istana Kepatihan* (ST)-Kepatihan Palace (TT)

This cultural term is translated by applying literal strategy. The literal meaning of lexical '*istana*' is translated into 'palace' in the TT.

d. *Selendang warisan dari ayahnya* (ST)-a shawl she inherited from her father (TT)

The translation strategy applied for (d) is free translation. This type of translation is emphasizing on the content information of the ST and often 'sacrifice' the structure and grammatical form of the ST. '*Selendang warisan*' can syntactically can be translated into 'inherited shawl' but the translation becomes 'a shawl she inherited from...'; there is additional determiner of the word 'a' in the beginning of the phrase.

The cultural terms of organization, custom and ideas are as follows:

e. *Ksatria* (ST) – As a knight (TT)

This cultural term applied the translation strategy of literal translation by having additional information of the word 'as' and determiner 'a'. Taking the equivalent issue, the word 'ksatria' is equivalent, and can be translated into 'knight'. However, the result of the translation of the TT is seen 'as a knight'.

f. *Ajian* (ST) – all of his energy (TT)

This cultural term applied free translation similar to (d). The word '*ajian*' is translated by paraphrase in the TT into 'all of his energy'. The translation tries to transfer the closest meaning in the TT by taking the core idea of energy equal to 'ajian'

CONCLUSION

Based on the above discussion, it can be found that there are three categories of cultural terms found in the literary work entitled Ini Banyuwangi-Sri Tanjung Hidup Kembali. The categories are ecological culture, material culture and organization, customs and ideas. The translation strategies applied in this literary works are word for word, literal, faithful, free, adaptation, idiomatic and communicative. The dominant strategies applied is adaptation strategy, and the least applied is idiomatic translation.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to extend our gratitude to Udayana University through the Institute of Research and Community Service for giving opportunity and support our research. We also would like to extend our gratitude to English Department students, Desak Intan and Desak Tia who have assisted us with data collection.

REFERENCES

1. Baker, Mona(ed). (2000) *Routledge Encyclopedia of Translation Studies*. London: Routledge
2. Baker, Mona. 1992. *In Other Words a Coursebook on Translation*. London: Routledge.
3. Bassnett, S. (002) *Translation Studies*. 3rd.ed. New York : Routledge
4. Catford, J.C, (1978). "A Linguistic Theory of Translation: An Essay in Applied Linguistic: Oxford University Press
5. Hatim, B & Munday, J.(2004) *Translation : An Advanced Resource Book*. New York: Routledge
6. Larson, M. (1998). *Meaning-Based Translation: A Guide to Cross-Language Equivalence*. 2nd.ed. New York: University Press of America
7. Newmark, Peter. 1988. *A Textbook of Translation*. New York : Prentice Hall
8. Newmark, P., "Approaches to Translation", Pergamon Press, pp. 27
9. Nida. E.A. (1975) *Language Structure and Translation*. Standford: Standford Univ Press

10. Denscombe, M. (1998) *The Good Research Guide*. Philadelphia: Open University Press.
11. Djajasudarma, T. Fatimah. (1993) *Metode Penelitian Linguistik: Ancangan, Metode Penelitian dan Kajian*. Bandung: PT. Eresco.
12. Sudaryanto. (1993) *Metode dan Aneka Teknik Analisis Bahasa*. Yogyakarta: Duta Wacana University Pres
13. Venuti, L. (2000). *The translation reader*. Routledge
14. Vinay, J. P., & Darbelnet, J. 1958. *Stylistique Compar ée du Francais et de l' Anglais: Méthode de Traduction*. In *Comparative Stylistics of French and English: A Methodology for Translation*. John Benjamins Publishing.
15. Vinay, J. P. and Darbelnet, J. 2000. A Methodology for Translation. In: Venuti, L. (ed.) *The Translation Studies Reader*. Routledge.

Cite this Article: Sang Ayu Isnu Maharani, I G A Istri Aryani (2024). Translation of Cultural Terms in Literary Work "Ini Banyuwangi Sri Tanjung Hidup Kembali". International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 7(12), 8682-8687, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V7-i12-04>